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Aims and Scope

Pentecostal Education (formerly The Pentecostal Educator) semiannually e-publishes scholarly and practical articles related to theological education within the Pentecostal tradition to encourage the continuing maturation of Pentecostal theological education. It is intentionally practical, applied, and international.

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International Church of the Foursquare: Formal Education

Gary Matsdorf

Abstract

Formal ministry training and education have been integral to the International Church of the Foursquare Gospel since its inception in 1923. Although the primary means of training in its 100-year history has developed mostly along the lines of One-Year Ministry Certificates from Schools of Ministry and ongoing informal leadership training seminars, it does have six degree-granting institutions globally offering accredited degrees, including terminal degrees. This article highlights four of Foursquare's six colleges/universities.

Keywords: Aimee Semple McPherson, formal and informal training, Life Pacific University, Asia LIFE University, LIFE Theological Seminary, New International University

January 1, 2023, the Foursquare denomination celebrated 100 years of ministry that began with the opening of Angelus Temple in the Los Angeles suburb of Echo Park on January 1, 1923. Shortly after its opening, Angelus Temple's founder, evangelist Aimee Semple McPherson, established "The Echo Park Evangelistic and Missionary Training Institute." The training institute reflected Mrs. McPherson's belief that ministry leadership required discipleship and formal training. The training institute was soon renamed L.I.F.E. (Lighthouse of International Foursquare Evangelism) Bible College and moved into an adjacent five-story building.

As Foursquare spread around the world (having a presence in 156 nations as of 2024), its modified episcopal form of government meant that each nation autonomously determined its own educational approach and standards for licensed ministers. Most nations chose (and still choose) not to require a ministry degree for licensed ministers and did not replicate

L.I.F.E.¹ Instead, Foursquare embraced non-degree granting training in either One-Year Ministry Certificate granting Schools of Ministry and/or ongoing ministry training seminars (informal training). The scope and theology of this approach are explained in detail in *Pentecostal Education*, Volume 8, Number 2, the article “Discipleship and Leadership Training.”

Despite not requiring a degree (or any minimum formal training), Foursquare U.S. continued to expand and develop L.I.F.E., which is called Life Pacific University today. Nigeria, South Korea, Canada, and Sri Lanka followed suit in opening degree-granting colleges and universities. Their histories are told below.²

Life Pacific University (LPU)³

The founder of the Foursquare Church clearly understood the need for Pentecostal formation and training. She was a “Holy Spirit preacher” who hosted numerous church services, healing crusades, and innovative radio and printed gospel messages. Still, she also felt strongly about education, so much so that when she founded the iconic Angelus Temple in Los Angeles in 1923, she also founded LPU, then called “The Echo Park Evangelistic and Missionary Training Institute.” Soon after, she dedicated an entire five-story building to education and training, renaming the school L.I.F.E. (Lighthouse of International Foursquare Evangelism) Bible College.⁴

LPU expanded throughout the 20th century, offering its first 4-year degree in the 1940s, and launched the Bachelor of Theology, Bachelor of Religious Education, and intercollegiate sports (basketball and baseball) in the 1950s. Another

¹ Even Foursquare (U.S.) dropped the formal education requirement in the late 1970s.

² Due to circumstances beyond the author’s control, Sri Lanka’s and Canada’s colleges will not be represented in this article.

³ This section of the article was written by Dr. Daniel Ruarte, Provost and Vice-President of Academic Affairs at LPU. More space is devoted to LPU than the other colleges because it is Foursquare’s founding university.

⁴ Nathaniel M. Van Cleave, *The Vine and The Branches: A History of the International Church of the Foursquare Gospel* (Los Angeles, CA: International Church of the Foursquare Gospel, 1992), 12.

milestone was reached in 1990 by relocating the university from Echo Park to a larger campus in San Dimas, California, its current home. This marked the beginning of several years of expansion and building projects.

In the 1980s, LPU began pursuing formal recognition from the U.S. Department of Education through accreditation associations recognized by the Council for Higher Education Accreditation (CHEA).⁵ Starting with accreditation from the Association of Biblical Higher Education (ABHE) in 1980, it obtained WASC Senior College and University Commission (WSCUC) candidacy in 2000,⁶ which culminated in full accreditation status in 2003. During this time, the name changed to Life Bible College and later, in 2019, to Life Pacific University. It is now under the leadership of President Angie Richey and has begun the initial accreditation process with the Association of Theological Schools (ATS) for its recently funded Life Pacific Seminary.⁷ These are all very significant accomplishments that represent a century of existence, institutional growth, and a commitment to formal higher education for ministry leaders.

The Mission of LPU

Life Pacific University is an institution of biblical higher education existing for the transformational development of students into leaders prepared to serve God in the Church, the workplace, and the world.

The Vision of LPU

Life Pacific University is recognized worldwide as a Pentecostal institution, within the Foursquare tradition, characterized by a diverse community of Spirit-empowered students, scholars, and practitioners whose hearts and minds are devoted to Christ and His kingdom.

⁵ Life Pacific University is a CHEA member institution, see online at <https://www.chea.org/life-pacific-university>.

⁶ For the WSCUC landing page for Life Pacific University, see: <https://www.wscuc.org/institutions/life-pacific-university>.

⁷ For LPU's launch of Life Pacific Seminary, see: <https://lifepacific.edu/seminary>.

LPU's Distinctives

- Scripture is LPU's authoritative guide for faith and practice and the foundation for how LPU thinks, learns, lives, and ministers (2 Timothy 3:16).
- LPU is a grace-based community that is exemplified by excellence organizationally and Christ-like character individually (Ephesians 2:11-22; John 15; Romans 8:28-30; Galatians 5:22-25/Ephesians 5:15-20).
- LPU reflects 1) Foursquare heritage and its appeal for moderation in doctrine and practice; 2) a Pentecostal ethos and Spirit-empowered lifestyle; 3) women in senior leadership in ministry; 4) Indigenous empowerment; and 5) an integrated interdenominational mission to take the gospel to the ends of the earth (Titus 1:7-9; Ephesians 4:11-13; Acts 1:4-8).
- LPU displays global awareness through celebrating diversity, understanding its place in the world and the far-reaching impact of decisions and actions, and innovatively engaging the world (1 Corinthians 12:12-31; Matthew 28:19-20; John 17:15-19).

LPU's ultimate objective is the preparation of leaders who will serve God wholeheartedly, taking the message of God's kingdom to the ends of the earth. While LPU is an educational institution of the Foursquare Church, more than one-third of the current student body comes from other denominations. The university and its founding movement value interdenominational cooperation⁸ and continue to pursue the ongoing fulfillment of its mission and vision.

Current and Future Degree Offerings⁹

- Undergraduate Programs: BA in Biblical Studies, BA in Ministry, BA in Business Administration, BA in Human Development and Psychology, BA in Mass

⁸ 2023/24 Full-Time faculty Handbook. Office of Academic Affairs and Provost Office. Life Pacific University.

⁹ For Life Pacific University Academic Offerings, see <https://lifepacific.edu/academics>.

Communication, BA in Worship, Arts and Media, Online BA in Organizational Management, Online BA in Ministry and Leadership.

- Graduate Programs: MA in Strategic Leadership, MA in Leadership (Spanish), MA in Theological Studies, MA in Counseling, Master of Business Administration (MBA), Master of Divinity (MDiv.)
- Non-Credit Certificates: Certificate in Biblical Foundations (English and Spanish), Certificate in Chaplaincy (English and Spanish), Certificate in NextGen Ministries, and Certificate in Theology (coming soon).
- Life Pacific University-Virginia Campus:¹⁰ In 2024, LPU received full accreditation and permission from the State Council of Higher Education for Virginia (SCHEV) and its accreditors to offer its full BA in Ministry program at her campus in Virginia. LPU is excited about this and knows that many students on the East Coast will benefit from this new offering.¹¹
- Doctor of Ministry (English and Spanish): One significant project underway is the first terminal degree to be offered by LPU. This has been a dream of many and is a significant investment that LPU is working to accomplish by 2026.¹²

Major Grants

For the first time in its history, LPU has received grants totalling over five million dollars since 2022.

¹⁰ L.I.F.E. opened a Midwest campus in Mount Vernon, Ohio, in 1957 where it remained until moving to Virginia in 1988.

¹¹ A new BA in Ministry is offered at the Virginia Campus. See <https://lifepacific.edu/news/lpuva-to-offer-on-campus-b-a-degree/>.

¹² This has been approved internally by our faculty, provost council, and board of trustees, but it is only in the initial phase of accreditation. Review by our accreditors (WSCUC, ABHE) is pending and must be finalized before we can admit or enroll any students. This should be completed and approved by 2026.

Lilly Pathways for Tomorrow: Developing Hispanic Pastors and Leaders (\$1,464,274).¹³ This grant has allowed LPU to increase the quality and promotion of its Hispanic offerings, including its MA in Leadership in Spanish and Spanish-language-based certificates. This also enables LPU to create multiple micro-certificates that will be offered at a meager cost to help develop Hispanic pastors and leaders. The grant also provides coaching opportunities and enhances LPU's programs. The motto, "From Certificate to Doctorate," bespeaks a pathway for the education and growth of Hispanic leaders. LPU is grateful for this opportunity and sees it as a blessing for the further development of leaders and influence.

Student Success Initiative: The Department of Education HSI grant (\$2,369,725).¹⁴ This grant allows LPU to offer a wide variety of support to its undergraduate student population, especially for academically underprepared students from high school and entering the university context. It is common knowledge that the first two semesters in college are the most difficult, and many students quit (in academic terms, they "drop out"). This causes retention to suffer, and those most affected are the students. The grant supports students by offering a summer bridge program, where they can go through an intensive academic and fun-filled program that prepares them to be successful in their first year of college and beyond. The grant also offers funds to support students with counseling and other needs and a component that includes faculty development and training certifications in helping students succeed.

Lilly Compelling Preaching: Enhancing Preaching Skills (\$1,249,176).¹⁵ The preaching grant is significant and a blessing for students in LPU's School of Theology and Ministry and current pastors and leaders. The grant consists of three

¹³ For more details of this grant, see <https://lifepacific.edu/news/5-million-lilly-endowment-shared-grant-awarded-to-lpu-apu-and-labi/>.

¹⁴ For more details on this grant, see <https://lifepacific.edu/news/lpu-awarded-2-3-million-u-s-department-of-education-federal-grant/>.

¹⁵ For more details on this grant, see <https://lifepacific.edu/news/lpu-awarded-lilly-grant/>.

activities—developing a Preaching Institute for aspiring preachers, hosting an annual preaching conference with top-quality workshops and speakers, and creating a digital repository called “Ministry Toolkit” that will resource pastors and leaders as they search for content and materials to develop their weekly sermons. These will be done from a Spirit-filled and Christ-centered perspective, covering some of the most important topics, doctrines, and aspects preachers deal with all the time.

New Centers and Departments, 2020-2024

Recently, as LPU has continued to pursue more excellent ways to fulfill its mission and vision through the development of centers and departments that can accelerate and help it focus on important tasks, LPU restructured its academic office with the installment of its first provost position and two colleges/schools, the School of Theology and Ministry (STM) and the School of Arts and Sciences (SAS) with their respective deans (see below). LPU also established a Prayer Chapel at the center of its academic building as a place where students and guests can come to pray or participate in hosted services. Other recent major accomplishments include the establishment of:

- The Center for Global Pentecostal Studies and Practice (CGPSP)¹⁶
- The Center for Educational Excellence (CEE)
- Life Pacific Seminary (LPS)¹⁷
- The School of Arts and Sciences (SAS)
- The School of Theology and Ministry (STM)

A2 University Designation (Acts Two)

Life Pacific University is an academic engine for the kingdom of God, the Foursquare denomination, and Pentecostal

¹⁶ See the article on the launch of the new Center for Global Pentecostal Studies and Practice at: <https://lifepacific.edu/news/a-new-beginning-lpus-seminary-and-center-for-global-pentecostal-studies-practice/>.

¹⁷ Life Pacific Seminary officially launched in 2023; for more detailed information and a welcome video by its director, see LPU’s website: <https://lifepacific.edu/seminary/>.

movements around the world. There are just a few fully accredited Pentecostal institutions,¹⁸ and LPU is Foursquare's primary university in the United States. Life Pacific University serves with a Holy Spirit vision of resembling a new, yet not so new, concept of being recognized as an "Acts 2 University" (an Acts 2 institution).¹⁹ LPU does not want to be just another Christian university; it strives to stand strong as a biblical university, holding on through its 100-year development to the required thirty units of Bible and ministry classes for all students and majors. LPU's highest aspiration, therefore, is to be recognized more and more as an "Acts 2 University."

In the higher education world, many universities seek an R1 designation,²⁰ the most prestigious recognition for research institutions. However, LPU would rather be recognized as a "Spirit-filled and Christ-centered" institution, defined by a strong Pentecostal ethos and a call to develop leaders for God's mission in the world who are radically passionate about God, His presence, and His kingdom! An "Acts 2 University" not only integrates "faith and learning," it goes deeper to integrate "Spirit and learning"; it is not just pedagogy or teaching, but Pentecostal pedagogy and teaching, within all its varied topics and subjects. A chapel at a Christian university might entail worship, preaching, and announcements. A chapel at an Acts 2 University entails worship, preaching, altar calls, prophetic words, laying on of hands, and a powerful move of the Holy

¹⁸ For the purposes of this article, "fully accredited" means holding accreditation with WSCUC. This accrediting association is the highest level of academic accreditation.

¹⁹ This concept came at one of LPU's Executive Cabinet Day Away work retreats. After a devotional time and prayer with Lew and Angie Richey, together with LPU's VP of Student Life, George Bostanic, and VP of Enrollment and Marketing, Sara Huson, Daniel Ruarte shared this vision with them of an Acts 2 University. In academia, an R1 institution is a top research university, and many universities strive to receive this distinguished designation. LPU believes it should strive to receive an Acts 2 designation, which attests to its dedication to living out a Pentecostal ethos and Acts 2 principles.

²⁰ For more information on what the R1, R2, and R3 designation means see: <https://carnegieclassifications.acenet.edu/carnegie-classification/research-designations/>.

Spirit within the student body. For these dynamics LPU wants to be recognized; this is its badge of honor and academic designation. Becoming an A2 University is based on LPU's long-standing vision which still drives the university in this direction; its leadership works diligently to facilitate an atmosphere of academic learning, biblical discipleship, and the powerful move of the Holy Spirit. Is LPU fully there yet? This writer thinks not. But there has been great progress towards this end,²¹ and everyone at LPU wants to pursue more of God and more of His presence, believes it is possible, and continues to pray to see a massive spiritual breakthrough. LPU wants to better partner together with pastors, churches, leaders, institutions, and movements to collaborate in the kingdom of God by providing high quality training and education whose graduates will impact the world for Christ.²²

*Asia LIFE University (ALU)*²³

Asia LIFE University (ALU) was established in 1972. The founding chairperson of the board of directors was Rev. Seen-Ok Ahn. The first president was Foursquare American missionary, Rev. Evelyn Thompson, and the current president is Dr. Sarah Yongnan Jeon Ahn. The founding philosophy of the university, which continues today, is to establish Christian leaders who emphasize the works, gifts, and ministry of the Holy Spirit based on one's personal experience with the Holy Spirit and consistent with Pentecostal theology. At present, thirty-one professors are teaching in their fields of expertise, and approximately 200 students are enrolled on campus annually in the master's and doctoral programs. About forty students from various countries are engaged annually in the online learning program. ALU is accredited by the Ministry of Education of the Korean Government and the Asia Theological Association.

²¹ Regarding an "outpouring of the Holy Spirit at LPU," see at <https://lifepacific.edu/news/outpouring-of-the-holy-spirit-at-lpu/>.

²² For more information, send inquiries to druarte@lifepacific.edu or academics@lifepacific.edu.

²³ This section of the article was written by Dr. Kwang-jin Jang, Professor of Systematic Theology at ALU.

History of ALU's Global Involvement

In addition to various master's and doctoral degree programs offered in the Korean language for Korean-speaking students, ALU has offered a Master of Divinity degree in English since 1998, inviting foreign leaders on campus to educate them and then send them back to serve their own people upon graduation. Many graduates who received theological education have dedicated themselves to the kingdom of God around the world. Over the past twenty-five years, 120 leaders from thirty-three countries across Asia, Europe, Africa, Central Asia, and the USA have graduated from ALU in the English degree track.

In 2017, ALU offered a Master of Divinity program in a city in China to educate Chinese leaders. The students were all recent graduates from a renowned university in China. Since graduating, they have been serving the Lord in different cities in China. ALU also offered an MA in Religious Studies program for Kazakh leaders via Zoom during the Covid-19 pandemic. The graduates are now ministering to Muslims in their country.

Since 2004, ALU has offered a Master of Divinity program for missionaries working in Europe. During their summer and winter vacations, ALU professors travel to countries such as Italy and Germany to hold intensive courses for missionaries. Those engaged in missionary work in different countries in Europe join these courses. During the regular semester periods, ALU offers online courses for them. Approximately forty missionaries have graduated from this program.

ALU is making every effort to train and establish leaders globally. While the campus is in Daejeon, South Korea, ALU extends its reach to the world with confidence that this is a promising way to effectively evangelize the world by equipping leaders with a Spirit-led theological orientation and the empowerment of the Holy Spirit.

Recent Developments at ALU

In response to the rapidly diversifying pastoral field of the 21st century, and to nurture the abilities needed for the church and society, ALU has opened departments not only in theology but also in pastoral counseling, counseling psychology, social welfare, alternative education, beauty therapy, and culture and arts therapy. These programs meet the diverse needs of the

pastoral field and community. ALU educates and produces leaders who have understanding and integrated skills. Leaders trained in the gospel of Jesus Christ and the power of the Holy Spirit are doing their best to evangelize and disciple people in various churches and communities.

In Fall 2023, in keeping with the university's commitment to serve as a meaningful and useful institution in establishing leaders for Foursquare churches globally, ALU launched a new master's program called the Global Online MA in Theology. The recent pandemic showed APU's leadership the great potential for training and establishing Foursquare leaders in different countries using Zoom sessions and video lectures exclusively, allowing trainees to stay home and continue their ministries in their countries. ALU believes this delivery system is a great way to establish leaders for Foursquare churches globally, especially where local Foursquare churches desperately need young leaders trained for involvement in ministry. It is especially an effective pathway to train those in Muslim contexts.

A Vision of the Future and Plans for Advancement

Education at ALU emphasizes Pentecostal theology, which is in-depth theological study of the Holy Spirit, and Spirit-filled ministry and missions. Professors and staff at ALU pray regularly that leaders trained in the gospel of Jesus and the power of the Holy Spirit will be involved in ministries effectively doing their best to evangelize and disciple the nations.

Based on Christian values, ALU is also committed to cultivating creative and talented individuals for future societal engagement and to establishing field experts with both theoretical and practical skills in areas such as counseling, healing, education, music, arts, and social welfare.

LIFE Theological Seminary²⁴

LIFE Theological Seminary (formerly LIFE Bible College) is an accredited degree granting institution sponsored by the Foursquare Gospel Church in Nigeria. It was established in 1955 in Lagos State, Nigeria, by Rev. and Rev. Mrs. Harold

²⁴ This section of the article was written by Dr. Cletus Orgu, Provost of LIFE Theological Seminary.

Curtis, Foursquare American missionaries to Nigeria. The seminary started as a vocational open-air Bible school where men and women were trained for practical Christian ministry. It later developed into a night Bible college after the Foursquare Gospel Church in Nigeria was officially inaugurated. LIFE was fully indigenized in 1986 with its first Nigerian principal, Rev. James Temidara. Today it is a fully accredited institution offering various degrees.

LIFE Theological Seminary is one of the foremost seminaries in Africa and serves English-speaking students continent-wide. Through a thoughtfully designed academic curriculum, opportunities for practical ministry experience, deeply rooted spiritual formation, and academic excellence, students are trained to be Christian leaders and agents of transformation in their respective communities. LIFE has graduated thousands of Christian ministers from all walks of life and different denominations from Nigeria, Ghana, Togo, Benin Republic, Central Africa Republic, Cameroon, Sudan, Democratic Republic of Congo, Rwanda, and Sierra Leone. In addition to the main campus in Ikorodu (since 1958), there are several centers and satellite campuses in various cities throughout Nigeria. Two of the seminary's satellite campuses have evolved into the status of a college of theology—LIFE Colleges of Theology in Aba and in Abuja, Nigeria. LIFE also offers online studies.

LIFE is accredited by the Association for Christian Theological Education in Africa (ACTEA) and affiliated with the University of Ibadan (U.I). LIFE is a member of the Overseas Council (O.C.) and a member of the International Council for Evangelical Theological Education (ICETE). Life Pacific University in America also recognizes LIFE's certificate for its master's degree program.

LIFE offers a certificate in Christian Ministry, a certificate and diploma in Music, a diploma in Theology, and a Bachelor of Theology, Master of Theology, and Doctor of Ministry/Philosophy (DMin/PhD) in Theology. In addition, LIFE organizes various academic-spiritual programs to further equip and educate students. These include the Annual Spiritual Life Retreat, an annual Social Weekend (a time of reflection on

topical national issues), an annual Christian Education Conference, and frequent Faculty Lectureships.

LIFE's leadership is committed to expanding the influence of the seminary in the 21st century, especially in Africa. It remains committed to its founding vision: "admonishing and teaching everyone in all wisdom, so that we may present everyone fully mature in Christ" (Col 1:28 NIV); its mission statement: "raising Holy Spirit-filled, fully and adequately equipped men and women for effective service to God, His Church and Humanity"; and its core values of spirituality, excellence, discipline, integrity, and competence.

*The New International University (TNIU)*²⁵

Higher education has always been a missional emphasis for the founders of The New International University, Drs. Peter and Gabriella van Breda. They view education as one of the best means to contribute to extending the kingdom of God in effective ways, especially in the majority world. They see formal higher education as "the new missions' frontier" believing that Christian leaders in every walk of life in the majority world are hungry for and in need of higher education.²⁶

²⁵ This section of the article was written by Dr. Gabriella van Breda, Chief Academic Officer at TNIU.

²⁶ TNIU's vision to democratize education is associated with the van Bredas' personal experiences and with research from organizations such as The World Bank/UNESCO and The Center for the Study of Global Christianity, Gordon-Conwell Theological Seminary. These organizations report a dearth of education in the majority world, particularly along Western patterns. If available in the majority world, it is generally only for limited sectors of the upper class. See: The State of Global Learning Poverty Update, Conference Edition, June 23, 2022. <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/e52f55322528903b27f1b7e61238e416-0200022022/original/Learning-poverty-report-2022-06-21-final-V7-0-conferenceEdition.pdf>. See also: Gordon Conwell University, <https://gordonconwell.edu/center-for-global-christianity/research/quick-facts/>. Paul House, Joost Nixon, "Incarnational Pastoral Training in the Majority World: An Interview with Dr. Paul House," *Journal of Global Christianity*, January 7, 2022. <https://trainingleadersinternational.org/jgc/139/incarnational->

This missional understanding, together with anecdotal evidence from their leadership on three continents over three decades, was the impetus for founding TNIU as an online university in 2017.²⁷ It is headquartered in Bellevue, Washington. TNIU was registered with the Washington State Student Achievement Council in 2017 and is accredited by the Asia Theological Association (ATA).

TNIU delivers accessible, affordable, biblical, missional, and practical higher education to pastors and leaders in twenty-two countries (2024), most of whom are in the majority world. As such, TNIU's degree courses are developed, structured, and delivered in a way that accentuates community transformation as the outcome of personal, professional, and pastoral educational development, often in the context of poverty, civil unrest, and Christian faith persecution.

In addition to gaining accreditation with ATA, TNIU's significant developments include:

- Fully online accredited degree programs utilizing synchronous and asynchronous learning models.
- Free access to online library resources for all students.
- A global supervising faculty.
- Multi-ethnic, cross-cultural student cohorts.
- A fee structure that makes Christian education affordable for the masses.
- Delivering education to leaders in their home country, thus eliminating the need for leaders to leave their cultural contexts to access higher education.

TNIU's future goals include: 1) offering degree programs in languages other than English, and 2) local context mentoring partnerships that facilitate student achievement and advancement. This latter is in keeping with TNIU's perspective

pastoral-training-in-the-majority-world-an-interview-with-dr-paul-house-author-of-bonhoeffers-seminary-vision; and Ashish Chrispal, "Restoring Missional Vision in Theological Education: The Need for Transformative Pastoral Training in the Majority World," Lausanne Movement, September 2019. <https://lausanne.org/global-analysis/restoring-missional-vision-theological-education#endnote-3>.

²⁷ The online nature of TNIU's degree programs allows leaders to study together with a cohort of other global students while remaining within their own country contexts.

that graduates are community influencers, whose critical thinking skills and training impact community decision-making at the corporate, political, and societal levels. As such, when Christian pastors and community leaders are equipped educationally, the ripple effect is better spiritual, mental, and physical care for marginalized groups. Spirituality and religious activity have been a source of healing, comfort, and relief for multitudes of people for thousands of years. While spirituality is expressed in diverse ways, medical research links the integration and practice of spirituality with better mental health outcomes, enhanced feelings of positivity, hopefulness, and improved psychological well-being. TNIU believes that this is all the more so when, higher education trains Christian leaders with a Bible-based curriculum.

Gary Matsdorf (gmatsdorf@foursquare.org), a minister of the Foursquare Church, serves as the Global Education Coordinator for the Foursquare Church and Chair of the Foursquare Global Doctrine Committee and the Foursquare's representative to the World Alliance for Pentecostal Theological Education. His publications include the *Spirit-Filled Life Bible*, co-edited with Jack Hayford.